

Optimum concrete mix proportion with ratio 1:1.5:3

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Abstract - The concrete mix ratio of 1:1.5:3 is still widely used in the construction of reinforced cement concrete (R.C.C.) structures. In a design mix prepared according to Indian Standards, the water-cement ratio is explicitly specified along with the proportions of the concrete ingredients. The water-cement ratio significantly influences both the compressive strength and the workability of concrete. During testing, cube specimens are evaluated to determine their compressive strength, which is then compared with the desired target strength. Therefore, determining the optimum water-cement ratio and mix proportions of materials is essential to achieve the required strength and performance characteristics of concrete. Attempts have been made to find optimum water cement ratio along with the variation in the ratio among coarse aggregate 20mm and 10mm size.

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a composite material composed mainly of cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, and water. The strength and durability of concrete depend primarily on the proportioning of these constituents and the water-cement ratio. The mix proportion 1 : 1.5 : 3 is one of the most widely used nominal mixes for producing medium-strength concrete. It is assumed that the ratio of concrete mix 1:1.5:3 is treated equivalent to M20 grade of concrete. Normally concrete mix is design in India as per IS:10262. But somewhere the ratio 1:1.5:3 is still used without any information about water cement ratio. Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials in the world. Owing to its unique combination of workability, mechanical strength, durability, and the wide availability of raw materials, concrete has become highly versatile and attractive for various civil engineering applications [1]. Each concrete application in the construction industry demands a particular mix composition to satisfy performance parameters such as workability, durability, and compressive strength. Therefore, designing a suitable concrete mix is essential to ensure that the final product meets the desired performance criteria. To achieve this, engineers employ the concrete mix design process, which involves selecting appropriate raw materials and determining their proportions to produce a mix that attains the required physical and chemical properties [2]. Most existing concrete mix design methods rely on empirical relationships, charts, and graphs derived from experimental studies. While they follow similar fundamental principles, only minor variations exist among them in determining mix

proportions [3]. Common traditional approaches include the American Concrete Institute (ACI) mix design method and the British mix design method [4]. According to DeRousseau [1], conventional mix proportioning can be classified into two main categories: prescriptive specifications and performance-based specifications. The prescriptive approach provides a step-by-step procedure to calculate the quantity of each component, whereas the performance-based approach focuses on achieving a specified property value without imposing strict guidelines. In the latter, the designer determines the desired performance criteria and selects appropriate quantities of cement, water, and aggregates to ensure the mixture meets the target property. Although traditional methods remain valuable, they exhibit several limitations. One major drawback is the insufficient consideration of Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) and their influence on concrete properties. As SCMs increasingly replace portions of cement, they significantly affect mechanical properties such as compressive strength [4]. Another limitation is that traditional mix design methods fail to fully capture the complex, nonlinear relationships between mixture composition and concrete performance. Because the type and proportion of each constituent vary widely, the resulting properties cannot be predicted with precise quantitative accuracy. Furthermore, these methods typically yield satisfactory rather than optimized mix compositions—meeting target property values but not necessarily achieving the most efficient or sustainable design. Beyond traditional approaches, some researchers employ the Design of Experiments (DoE) framework to determine optimal concrete mix compositions. Compared to empirical methods, DoE can provide improved results due to systematic experimentation. However, optimization becomes computationally expensive and exponentially complex as the number of variables and their ranges increase [1]. Moreover, because of the high degree of nonlinearity between dependent and independent variables, regression-based predictive models often fail to produce accurate equations [5]. Consequently, neither traditional nor experimental approaches consistently achieve optimized mix designs. To address these challenges, computational methods have gained prominence for modeling the intricate relationships between input variables and resulting concrete properties [6]. These approaches—particularly mathematical programming and machine learning (ML)—enable more accurate modeling and optimization, often leading to superior solutions [7]. Both methods can be applied individually or in combination and are increasingly used to solve complex engineering problems. Researchers now explore these computational tools to predict concrete properties more efficiently, cost-effectively, and sustainably [8][9].

Numerous studies have reviewed the use of mathematical and ML-based models for predicting concrete performance or optimizing mix proportions. For example, Chaabene et al. [10] investigated ML models for forecasting mechanical properties of concrete, while another study systematically reviewed ML algorithms for predicting compressive strength [11]. Similarly, Song et al. [12] analyzed recent advancements in mix ratio optimization using ML and metaheuristic algorithms, highlighting ongoing progress in hybrid optimization models.

II METHODOLOGY

A total of 15 sets of cement concrete cubes of size 150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm were prepared for the study. The mixes were designed with varying water–cement ratios (W/C) and proportions of coarse aggregates (20 mm and 10 mm sizes). The proportions of 20 mm and 10 mm coarse aggregates were taken as 50:50, 60:40, and 75:25, while the water–cement ratios considered were 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, and 0.60. Each set of cubes was prepared in separate batches and cured in clean water for 28 days. After curing, all specimens were tested for compressive strength using a Compression Testing Machine (CTM). The samples were labeled according to their mix proportions. For example, a cube designated as Mix50-50-0.60 represents a mix containing 50% of 20 mm aggregate, 50% of 10 mm aggregate, and a water–cement ratio of 0.60. The coarse aggregate (C.A.) ratio is defined as the percentage proportion of 20 mm aggregate to 10 mm aggregate in the mix.

Table 1: Mix proportion of concrete mix with ratio 1:1.5:3

Mix	Cement (Kg)	Sand (Kg)	CA (20mm) (Kg)	CA (10mm) (Kg)	W/C	Average Strength (N/mm ²)
Mix50-50-0.60	5.1	7.65	7.65	7.65	0.60	22.56
Mix50-50-0.55	5.1	7.65	7.65	7.65	0.55	24.22
Mix50-50-0.50	5.1	7.65	7.65	7.65	0.50	30.43
Mix50-50-0.45	5.1	7.65	7.65	6.12	0.45	32.75
Mix50-50-0.40	5.1	7.65	7.65	7.65	0.40	40.58
Mix60-40-0.60	5.1	7.65	9.18	6.12	0.60	18.77
Mix60-40-0.55	5.1	7.65	9.18	6.12	0.55	22.24
Mix60-40-0.50	5.1	7.65	9.18	6.12	0.50	24.56
Mix60-40-0.45	5.1	7.65	9.18	6.12	0.45	34.09
Mix60-40-0.40	5.1	7.65	9.18	6.12	0.40	43.92
Mix75-25-0.60	5.1	7.65	11.48	3.83	0.60	23.35
Mix75-25-0.55	5.1	7.65	11.48	3.83	0.55	25.48
Mix75-25-0.50	5.1	7.65	11.48	3.83	0.50	30.82
Mix75-25-0.45	5.1	7.65	11.48	3.83	0.45	34.18
Mix75-25-0.40	5.1	7.65	11.48	3.83	0.40	35.79

Fig. 1. Compressive strength for C.A. percentage ratio 50-50

Fig. 2. Compressive strength for C.A. percentage ratio 60-40

Fig. 3. Compressive strength for C.A. percentage ratio 75-25

Fig. 4. Comparison of compressive strength for ratio of C.A.

III RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The compressive strength of concrete is significantly influenced by the water–cement (W/C) ratio and the proportion of coarse aggregate sizes used in the mix. To evaluate these effects, concrete cubes were cast using the nominal mix proportion of 1 : 1.5 : 3, with varying W/C ratios and different size combinations of coarse aggregates (20 mm and 10 mm). Fig. 1, Fig. 2, and Fig. 3 show the average compressive strength of concrete cubes after 28 days of curing for different water–cement ratios and percentage combinations of coarse aggregates as 50:50, 60:40, and 75:25 (20mm : 10mm) respectively. Although the cement content plays an important role as the primary binding material in concrete, the compressive strength of concrete depends on several other factors such as the water–cement (W/C) ratio, aggregate size distribution, curing conditions, and mixing uniformity. Since the mix proportion 1 : 1.5 : 3 is already well established and widely used in practice, the present study focuses mainly on the influence of W/C ratio and percentage variation of coarse aggregate sizes (20mm and 10mm) on the strength characteristics of concrete. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of compressive strength of concrete at different W/C ratio.

(a) Effect of water-cement ratio on concrete strength

From the test results and plotted curves, it is clearly evident that Abram's law is valid for all mix proportions. The compressive strength of concrete decreases as the W/C ratio increases, confirming the inverse relationship between these two parameters. It was observed that the compressive strengths obtained at W/C ratios of 0.45 and 0.55 were relatively close, indicating that beyond the optimum point, further reduction in water content has a diminishing effect on strength gain. The major variation in compressive strength with change in W/C ratio occurred in the mix where the coarse aggregate percentage ratio was 50:50 (20mm: 10mm).

(b) Effect of coarse aggregate (20mm and 10mm) percentage ratio on concrete strength

Significant variation in compressive strength was observed when the coarse aggregate proportion was 60:40, across all W/C ratios studied. This combination appears to provide better particle packing and interlocking, leading to higher strength values. In contrast, the least variation in compressive strength was found when the aggregate proportion was 75:25, suggesting that excessive dominance of a single aggregate size may reduce mix homogeneity. It can be stated that at a W/C ratio of 0.45, the compressive strength values were nearly the same for all coarse aggregate proportions, indicating that this ratio provides the optimum water content for proper hydration and aggregate bonding in the 1 : 1.5 : 3 mix.

IV CONCLUSIONS

This study was carried out to determine the effect of varying proportions of coarse aggregates (20 mm and 10 mm) and different water–cement ratios on the 1 : 1.5 : 3 concrete mix. Based on the results of the compressive strength tests, it can be concluded that for water–cement ratios of 0.45 and 0.55, all three combinations of coarse aggregate proportions (50:50, 60:40, and 75:25) produced comparable values of compressive strength. This indicates that within this range of water–cement ratios, the variation in the proportion of coarse aggregates has a relatively minor influence on the compressive strength of concrete.

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